

SUMMARY REPORT

NASA Earth Science and Industry Summit

Hosted by the U.S. Chamber of Commerce

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NASA Earth

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Executive Summary

The NASA Earth Science and Industry Summit, hosted by the U.S. Chamber of Commerce on February 2, 2026, served as a strategic forum to explore how NASA's Earth Science enterprise contributes to the engines of the American economy and how public and private sectors can align to unlock new opportunities in Earth Observation (EO). Approximately 130 participants representing agriculture, insurance, finance, energy, and utilities joined NASA scientists, commercial data providers, and analytics firms for a full-day program that included a NASA Earth expo, a fireside chat with industry leaders, a commercial data provider panel, and breakout listening sessions. The summit surfaced decision contexts, data needs, barriers-to-adoption, and collaboration opportunities.

What the Summit Delivered

The Summit brought together the full EO value chain—from data providers and commercial satellite operators to analytics platforms and major sector decision-makers—creating shared visibility into where adoption of satellite Earth information is accelerating and stalling. Insights emerged in three general areas:

- Priority use cases for all the five industry sectors represented at the summit;
- Barriers-to-adoption and areas for collaboration across the EO value chain; and
- Demonstration of EO data integration into industry workflows.

Overview of Industry Insights

Across every sector, participants shared that EO data drives real economic value, including improving operations, enhancing commercial products, strengthening business planning and risk assessment, and generating major cost savings.

NASA provides trusted, end-to-end Earth insight.

NASA offers a credible, openly accessible, decision-relevant foundation for the Earth Observation ecosystem, from missions and measurements to models and applications. Across sectors, stakeholders emphasized NASA's unique value in providing trusted, continuous, and scientifically grounded data that supports calibration, validation, downstream products, and high-stakes business decisions.

The main barrier is last-mile translation for scaled adoption.

The highest leverage opportunity for end users is a stronger pathway from Earth observations to operational use, supported by better packaging, training, and repeatable engagement models.

Workforce development is a cross-sector need.

Capability varies widely across—and even within—industries, resulting in strong demand for training and practitioners who can bridge Earth science and operational decision-making. Industry outlined a need for help in training the next generation of EO data practitioners and “translators” to take NASA Earth science from awareness to operational use. Repeatable, role-based training pathways that build skills in the full workflow, from dataset selection and validation through cloud-ready processing and decision integration, are desired.

Industry is asking for deeper, sustained collaboration.

End users want co-development through pilots, working sessions, and real demonstrations, coupled with success metrics so solutions are validated in operational workflows, value is quantified, and adoption can scale beyond one-off briefings.

Awareness and maturity in using NASA Earth science varies.

Utilities and finance described being earlier in the journey and needing clearer translation into workflows, while insurance and agriculture tend to be more mature users with established pipelines. NASA's ability to demonstrate sector-specific use cases would help to enable increased understanding and spark actionable ideas.

Reliability and continuity are business requirements.

Industry needs predictable availability, visibility into end-of-life transitions, and confidence that what they integrate today will remain supported on multi-year business timescales. As one finance participant noted, integration is only “worth it” if continuity is a real commitment.

AGRICULTURE

Use Cases

- Irrigation/water risk decisions
- Drought and heat stress early warning
- Post-event impact assessment
- Trustworthy sustainability indicators for sourcing and supply chain risk management

Opportunities

- Decision-ready products that fit real farm and supply chain workflows, delivered through trusted intermediaries with low-friction access, targeted training, and field-relevant insights
- More science-farmer-data creator forums like NASA Acres
- Economic metrics to demonstrate the value of satellite data
- Improved data latency to support timely decisions
- Accelerated co-creation through deeper engagement with key players such as data aggregators, associations, and extension networks
- Streamlined technology transfer to support sustained commercialization

FINANCE

Use Cases

- Climate and nature risk screening across assets and portfolios
- Stress testing and scenario analysis
- Corporate and financial disclosure reporting
- Integration of geospatial indicators into analyst and risk workflows

Opportunities

- Improved discoverability of NASA datasets so financial users can more easily identify, assess, and access the products most relevant to their workflows
- Open-source packages that can be more readily adopted within highly regulated IT environments
- Decision-grade datasets with strong provenance and validation, packaged for easy ingestion, API access, and targeted workforce training to help move from pilots to institutional use
- Engagement with sustainability standard-setting bodies, such as Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD), to help align Earth science with emerging finance and disclosure needs

INSURANCE

Use Cases

- Hazard and exposure intelligence for underwriting and pricing
- Parametric trigger design
- Rapid event impact assessment for response and claims (wind, flood, wildfire/smoke)
- Portfolio accumulation risk monitoring across time horizons

Opportunities

- High-confidence, validated hazard layers and benchmarks that are analysis-ready, easy to operationalize, and supported by clear continuity signals
- Sustained engagement in insurance and reinsurance venues to co-design fit-for-purpose products
- Lower-latency products that better support time-sensitive insurance workflows such as event response
- Better characterization of emerging perils such as convective windstorms, subsidence, ice loading, and critical infrastructure exposure
- Expanded use of long-term archived products to strengthen catastrophe model calibration, validation, and trend analysis
- Clearer certification pathways for AI-enabled models used in insurance decision-making
- Clearer pixel-level uncertainty information to help users assess fitness for use in underwriting, pricing, and risk decisions

ENERGY

Use Cases

- Asset and infrastructure siting and resilience planning
- Operational monitoring of hazards and disruptions
- Emissions and sustainability tracking
- Integration of Earth data into enterprise risk and planning systems

Opportunities

- Reliable, always-on data products that are easy to discover and integrate, along with guidance to help users navigate public and commercial data options without costly trial and error
- Continued investment in Earth system models for planning and risk assessment
- Calibration and validation support that helps energy users assess data quality, uncertainty, and fitness for use across applications
- Stronger use of boundary organizations as connectors and clearer user pathways that reduce dependence on expensive consultants

UTILITIES

Use Cases

- High-resolution data for water management
- Extreme event forecasting and monitoring
- Soil moisture and subsidence indicators for pipe integrity and infrastructure risk
- Algal bloom and water supply monitoring and forecasting

Opportunities

- Decision-ready, reliable Earth science data with continuity over time
- Products with high technology readiness levels given that the sector is very conservative
- NASA-funded pilots and early-adopter pathways to de-risk adoption
- Harmonized datasets that integrate into Esri/GIS workflows
- Alignment between NASA and commercial datasets, including Commercial Satellite Data Acquisition (CSDA) holdings
- Training tied to operational workflows

Note: Utility company representation was more limited than in other sectors; these findings should be treated as directional and validated through follow-on engagement.

Role of Commercial Satellite and Data Providers in the EO Ecosystem

The summit illuminated the evolving role of commercial data providers in the EO ecosystem, particularly through insights shared during the commercial data provider panel. Despite rapid advances in capability and burgeoning demand for their data, EO adoption challenges are systemic in nature, impacting the commercial satellite sector and NASA alike.

Commercial satellite data providers offer scaling and agility that are powerful for business.

Capabilities are growing across the board, with advances in both instrumentation and fleet size offering frequent revisits. Working in complement to NASA and other open data sources, commercial providers help to meet industry needs for timeliness, flexibility, and application-specific delivery.

Use case translation remains critical.

Many providers demonstrate strong technical capability, but there is a gap in translating EO into decision-ready products that fit real workflows and deliver measurable outcomes. Some users mentioned the need for data at the fit-for-purpose level, rather than more advanced products. Providers did mention moving “up the stack,” with growing emphasis on delivering ready-to-use outputs that reduce integration burden.

Continuity is a business requirement.

Users need predictable availability for the long term. Commercial providers are including this in their planning. Robust pairing of public and commercial sources is also needed to create longer-term records and frame recent observations.

Alignment with public mission products is a trust signal.

Providers referenced calibration/alignment with openly available data from NASA and other public sources, underscoring the importance of compatibility.

Ecosystem engagement can accelerate uptake.

Trade associations and other mechanisms can help educate stakeholders, surface needs earlier, and broaden participation across the EO ecosystem.

Collaboration between commercial providers and NASA is wanted.

To address shared challenges, NASA can serve as a neutral convener and provide technological support.

Rapid innovation while maintaining interoperability.

Commercial providers’ innovation cycle is as short as 12 months; however, the challenge is balancing speed with consistency, such as advancing observation capabilities and generating value-added products while maintaining user satisfaction.

Priorities

The Summit moved the community from conversation to cooperation. The clearest path forward centers on five priorities:

Sustain engagement

Convene the full ecosystem regularly, including commercial satellite providers, not just end users.

Meet industry where decisions are made

Show up in sector forums with grounding in real operational timelines.

Develop decision-ready products

Build workflows that integrate public and private satellite data with the reliability, latency, and interoperability required by industry.

Invest in workforce development

Train the “translators” who can bridge Earth science and industry decision-making.

Accelerate interest to outcomes

Advance clear pilots, defined success metrics, and a visible front door for new partners to engage.

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Disclaimer

This summary captures key themes and anecdotes shared by attendees of the event. It does not reflect the views of the entire sector or industry, nor is it meant to be a comprehensive analysis. This summary is intended to reflect the conversation with these specific user communities and statements should not be interpreted as signaling any change in NASA's direction, priorities, or commitments.

